

Slime molds from Africa and Asia

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Abstract: Twenty species of mostly corticolous myxomycetes are reported from Africa and Asia, including such rarities as *Didymium sturgisii*, *Licea atricapilla*, *L. chelonoides*, *L. erectoides*, *Macbrideola oblonga*, and *M. scintillans*.

Keywords: bark, corticoles, microscopic, rare taxa

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Very few records exist for corticolous myxomycetes collected from the bark of living trees anywhere in Africa. The only records appear to be from Gambia (Härkönen, 1981) Tanzania (Ukkola, 1998) and Tunisia (Mitchell & Kylin, 1984). Casual collections of bark samples were made by friends and relatives on visits to various African countries.

Visits by friends to Nepal, Saudi Arabia, India (Sikkim region), and Russia (Lake Baikal region) provided opportunities to collect bark from living trees. The samples were cultured in standard moist chambers and the myxomycetes harvested. Voucher specimens are held in the personal herbarium of B. Ing. The results extend the known distribution of both rare and common species in an interesting way.

Arcyria minuta Buchet

Morocco: Marrakesh, on bark of unidentified tree, 2019, G. Lewis-Ing.

An uncommon lignicolous species, rarely found in bark cultures.

Calomyxa metallica (Berk.) Niewland

Saudi Arabia: Abha, on *Juniperus procera*, 2002, D. W. Minter.

A common and widespread species, probably cosmopolitan.

Didymium sturgisii Hagelst.

Saudi Arabia: Abha, on *Juniperus procera*, 2002, D. W. Minter.

A rare species known from America and Europe.

Echinostelium apitectum K.D. Whitney

Saudi Arabia: Abha, on *Juniperus procera*, 2002, D. W. Minter.

Sudan: Khartoum Botanic Garden, on *Tectona grandis*, 1984, E. B. Ing.

Originally described from North America this species is now known to be widespread in Europe and Asia. The species concept has recently been expanded to include *E. vanderpoelii* Nann.-Brem., Mitchell, Lakhan.& Chopra (Lado & Pando, 1997) and the material from Sudan fits the description of *E. vanderpoelii*, should the synonymy of these species be questioned.

Echinostelium brooksii K.D. Whitney

Ethiopia: Lalibela, unidentified tree, 1994, A. Waterfield.

Russia: Baikal, on *Betula* bark, and Khabarov, on *Pinus* bark, 1991, F. Wiseman.

India (Sikkim): Tsokha, on bark of unidentified tree, 1997, M. J. Gregory.

Widespread in Europe, the Americas, Turkey and previously reported from the Ukraine (Minter & Dudka, 1996).

Echinostelium colliculosum K.D. Whitney & H.W. Keller

Mali: Binyani escarpment, on *Tamarindus indica*, 1995, A. Waterfield.

Also reported from Tunisia (Mitchell & Kylin, 1984.)

Russia: Baikal, on *Betula* and *Pinus* bark, 1991, F. Wiseman.

Saudi Arabia: Abha, on *Juniperus procera*, 2002, D. W. Minter.

Widely distributed in Europe, the Americas and Asia; previously reported from the Ukraine and Turkey.

Echinostelium minutum de Bary

Seychelles: Mahe, on unidentified tree, 1985, M. Jones.

Cosmopolitan; reported from Gambia, Tanzania and Tunisia.

Enerthenema papillatum (Pers.) Rostaf.

Russia: Irkutsk, on *Pinus* bark, 1991, F. Wiseman.

Cosmopolitan; one of the commonest species on acid-barked trees, previously reported from most parts of Asia.

Licea atricapilla Nann.-Bremek. & Y. Yamam.

Nepal: Dumre, on bark of unidentified tree, 1995, M. J. Gregory.

India (Sikkim): Tsokha, on bark of unidentified tree, 1997, M. J. Gregory.

Described from Japan, and hitherto only known from the type collection (Nannenga-Bremekamp and Yamamoto, 1983) these collections provide an interesting extension of range.

Licea chelonoides Nann.-Bremek.

Sierra Leone: Lumbley Bay, Freetown, on unidentified tree, 1983, H. Davies.

Rather a rare species and previously only known from Europe.

Licea erectoides Nann.-Bremek. & Y. Yamam.

India (Sikkim): Tsokha, on bark of unidentified tree, 1997, M. J. Gregory.

Described from Japan and elsewhere known only from Hong Kong (Ing, 1987a) and Belize (Ing & Haynes, 1999.)

Licea kleistobolus G.W. Martin

Madeira: Funchal, on bark of unidentified tree, 2012, J. England.

Morocco: Marrakesh, on bark of unidentified tree, 2019, G. Lewis-Ing.
 Saudi Arabia: Abha, on *Juniperus procera*, 2002, D. W. Minter.
 India (Sikkim): Tsokha, on bark of unidentified tree, 1997, M. J. Gregory.
 Cosmopolitan; recorded from Bombay (Ing, 1983).

Licea parasitica (Zukal) G.W. Martin

Madeira: Funchal, on bark of unidentified tree, 2012, J. England.
 Mali: Lalibela, on unidentified tree, 1994, A. Waterfield.
 Morocco: Marrakesh, 2019, G. Lewis-Ing.
 Cosmopolitan and perhaps the most common corticolous myxomycete; reported from Tanzania and Tunisia.

Licea pedicellata (H.C.Gilb.) H.C.Gilb.

India (Sikkim): Tsokha, on bark of unidentified tree, 1997, M. J. Gregory.
 Widespread, in several continents; previously recorded from India.

Macbrideola oblonga Pando & Lado

Saudi Arabia: Abha, on *Juniperus procera*, 2002, D. W. Minter.
 A rare species known from a few sites in Europe and N. America.

Macbrideola scintillans H.C. Gilbert

India (Sikkim): Tsokha, on bark of unidentified tree, 1997, M. J. Gregory.
 A rare species, described from North America and elsewhere known only from Belize, Ireland and Japan.

Paradiacheopsis fimbriata (G.List.& Cran) Hertel

Russia: Baikal, on *Pinus* bark, 1991, F. Wiseman.
 Probably cosmopolitan on conifer bark; previously reported from Turkey and the Ukraine.

Perichaena chrysosperma (Currey) Lister

Madeira: Funchal, on bark of unidentified tree, 2012, J. England.
 Morocco: Marrakesh, on bark of unidentified tree, 2019, G. Lewis-Ing.

Physarum crateriforme Petch

India (Sikkim): Tsokha, on bark of unidentified tree, 1997, M. J. Gregory.
 Widespread in several continents; previously reported from India.

Stemonitis nigrescens Rex

Morocco: Marrakesh, on bark of unidentified tree, 2019, G. Lewis-Ing.
 This uncommon species is often synonymised with the lignicolous *S. fusca* but differs in size, spores and ecology.

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